

CORPORA AND LITERATURE**Mahmudova Dildora Murodilloyevna**

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Abstract. Literary corpora comprise poetry and fictional prose texts, such as novels, short stories and plays. They bring together the collected works of a single author or representative texts from a specific literary period. Since literary corpora are often available through powerful concordances, they are especially well suited for a quantitative and qualitative approach to comparative literary analysis, within or across different genres and historical periods. This paper attempts to analyze the relationship of corpus and literature.

Keywords: corpus, literature, corpora

Introduction. The analysis of literary texts using corpora is a common methodological approach in the field of stylistics. Stylistics, which is the study of style in language, is a sub-discipline of linguistics within applied linguistics. While stylisticians typically focus on analyzing literary texts, there is no reason why stylistics should be limited to this type of text. In fact, some stylisticians have applied the same analytical techniques to non-literary texts. However, the principles of stylistics are rooted in the study of literary texts, and corpora are valuable tools for testing hypotheses and theories about texts and stylistic effects. In recent years, the use of corpora has provided statistical evidence that supports foregrounding theory, a fundamental aspect of stylistics.

Foregrounding theory posits that an author's intentional linguistic choices play a crucial role in shaping their style. These choices give rise to specific stylistic effects, which can be observed at the overall authorial level, within a particular genre, or even in a specific text. According to this theory, the most significant stylistic elements are those that deviate from the established norms of language, whether those norms are external or internal to the text itself. Psychological studies have lent support to this theory by demonstrating that readers generally agree on what is considered foregrounded in a text.

However, determining the extent of foregrounding has historically been challenging due to limited access to frequency information about linguistic norms. The advent of large-scale electronic corpora has greatly facilitated this process, as it provides linguists with the necessary tools to analyze linguistic patterns and establish statistical norms. Some linguists have questioned the utility of relying on frequency information, even if it were readily available.

Nevertheless, these objections are flawed because understanding the statistical norms of language is crucial in determining whether a particular usage is indeed unusual and therefore foregrounded.

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